

Population Differences in National Finnish Grid Scales

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Summary

Scale is a key aspect in spatial data science in both vector and raster data for further analysis. There is a clear distinction between vector and raster data. However, there is not a clear distinction for scale in vector data. This paper focuses on population differences between three national Finnish vector grid data scales, which have minimum population restrictions when used for further analysis. The results show that 440,320 of the 5.5 million population of Finland are omitted in the finest spatial scale and 8,825 are omitted from the largest spatial scale, which has negative impacts for future spatial planning.

KEYWORDS: boundary delimitation, grid cells, multi scale, population, vector data.

1 Introduction

Scale has a clear definition for raster data as it is typically defined by resolution and extent (Goodchild, 2011), but scale in vector data is less well defined. In terms of extent, vector polygons come in all shapes and sizes, and the data within them are also not uniform. Typical vector data representations are in the form of postcode areas or municipalities, whereby the shape and size are not important since the boundary is well defined to researchers and those who live within them. These imagined boundaries have further impacts on results, depending on where the boundary splits an area- this is referred to as the “modifiable areal unit problem” (Openshaw et al., 1998). Consequently, grid cells are then a good solution to represent data due to the shapes and sizes being uniform. However, the data within the grid cells are still not uniform, so even though the represented scale is known, the data scale are still not known. When looking at human populations in particular, the grid cells do not have equal populations because people do not live uniformly.

It has been found that not all countries have national spatial open data sets that include equal population distributions, with Finland being one of them. Oshan et al. (2022) state that there is also a shortcoming in the “misspecification of scale”. Already in 1997, Tobler et al. had success in

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designing gridded raster data resulting in latitude/longitude quadrilaterals as bins for population information (Tobler et al., 1997). Grid cells are, therefore, not a new phenomenon, but they have rarely been evaluated for what implications these specific outputs have for further analysis. This paper focuses critically on three national Finnish grid vector data sets: the 250m grid which has a minimum population restriction of five people, and the 1km grid and 5km grid which have a minimum population restriction of 10 people for further analysis. These population restrictions have significant implications when considering how much of the population is omitted from further analysis. In this paper we investigate which populations are omitted in the three grid cell data sets and how this influences decision making for spatial planning.

2 Data

We place an emphasis on the whole of Finland as a case study area. Finland is in Northern Europe and lies to the east of Sweden. It has a population of approximately 5.5 million (Statistics Finland, 2020). All the three data sets contain the population from the year 2020 and the data sources are all from Statistics Finland (Statistics Finland, 2022). The 250m grid is private data and is available to researchers. It can be used for further analysis when there is a minimum of five people in each grid cell. The remaining two data sets are openly available. The 1km and 5km grids require a minimum population of 10 people in each grid cell for further analysis. The grid cells are assigned the municipality which has the largest surface area within it if it borders several municipalities. In 2020 there were 310 municipalities. The original data include only inhabited grid cells- in the figures the empty spaces contain no resident population. The cells are filtered into two categories: <5 and ≥ 5 for the 250m grid, or <10 and ≥ 10 for the 1km and 5km grids. The population structure sums are confidential if there are fewer than three residents over the age of 18 years old and are removed by Statistics Finland, meaning that populations are already missing from this data.

3 Differences in National Finnish spatial scales

Table 1 shows the grid polygon differences for both the polygon count and the population count. The polygon count has the most striking results. For the 250m grid only 19.2% of the data are left when filtering for a ≥ 5 minimum population that can be used for further analysis. This result increases when the size of the grid cell increases- 35.2% are left for the 1km grid and 81% are left for the 5km grid. In terms of the 250m grid, the remaining population is 91.9% which means that 440,320 people are removed from further analysis. For the 1km grid then 95.6% is remaining, meaning that 241,000 people are removed from further analysis. Finally, for the 5km grid then 99.8% is remaining, omitting only 8,825 people from further analysis.

Table 1: Removed data from grid cells when accounting for minimum populations

Data Set	Minimum Population	< Polygon Count	< Population Count
250m grid	<5	$512,931/634,807 = 80.8\%$	$440,320/5,455,832 = 8.1\%$
1km grid	<10	$63,817/98,513 = 64.8\%$	$241,000/5,472,034 = 4.4\%$
5km grid	<10	$1,969/10,364 = 19\%$	$8,825/5,472,034 = 0.16\%$

Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3 show the spatial distribution of remaining and removed grid cells for the 250m, 1km, and 5km respectively. Table 2 and Table 3 reveal the top and bottom five municipalities in terms of population loss, as well as by age brackets, and then their respective grid count loss. Table 4 only reveals the top five municipalities as the bottom 70 out of 310 municipalities keep 100% of their population. The bottom five contain four of the same municipalities in each of the tables: Kauniainen, Helsinki, Kerava, and Järvenpää. Kauniainen is Finland’s smallest municipality, covering only 6km², 83 grid cells, and a population of 10,333 when using the 250m grid. It covers five grid cells at the 1km grid with a population of 7,572 and has no grid cells in the 5km grid so it disappears at the 5km scale. Each of the 310 municipalities have a different population depending on the three scales since the grid cells are assigned the municipality which covers the largest surface area of the cell. This shows that the underlying structure of grid cell data need to be transparent and open to be able to interpret spatial evidence creation, and to allow for reproducible results.

Table 2: 250m grid top and bottom municipalities ranked by population removed

Label	Top Municipalities	Population (%)	Age 0-15	Age 16-64	65+	Grid (%)
A	Kumlinge	61	10	48	21	95.5
B	Luhanka	58	20	93	55	95.6
C	Rääkkylä	56	70	276	93	95.1
D	Sottunga	54.8	0	8	5	94.7
E	Kökar	53.8	3	37	20	94.9
Label	Bottom Municipalities	Population (%)	Age 0-15	Age 16-64	65+	Grid (%)
F	Vantaa	0.38	36	286	109	31.6
G	Järvenpää	0.29	9	47	15	22.9
H	Kerava	0.26	8	37	13	28.4
I	Helsinki	0.06	25	157	33	25.1
J	Kauniainen	0.04	0	4	0	2.4

Table 3: 1km grid top and bottom municipalities ranked by population removed

Label	Top Municipalities	Population (%)	Age 0-14	Age 15-64	65+	Grid (%)
A	Kumlinge	76.6	12	52	45	92.9
B	Rääkkylä	67.4	50	233	114	97.5
C	Luhanka	64.2	17	54	38	95.5
D	Brändö	60.7	11	85	36	92.3
E	Siikainen	59	51	167	74	94.1
Label	Bottom Municipalities	Population (%)	Age 0-14	Age 15-64	65+	Grid (%)
F	Järvenpää	0.083	6	13	9	10
G	Kerava	0.076	3	8	5	10.3
H	Mariehamn	0.027	0	0	0	12.5
I	Helsinki	0.024	8	45	29	9.9
J	Kauniainen	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4: 5km grid bottom municipalities ranked by population removed

Label	Top Municipalities	Population (%)	Age 0-14	Age 15-64	65+	Grid (%)
A	Utsjoki	19.8	19	65	56	70.6
B	Puolanka	15.3	33	129	75	71.8
C	Föglö	14.8	8	37	18	53.8
D	Hyrnsalmi	14.2	22	91	82	67.3
E	Kumlinge	14.1	2	7	7	55.6

In Finland, and most other countries, only the most densely populated major towns and cities will have the highest remaining inhabitants, and the most sparsely populated rural areas will have a smaller proportion of inhabitants left over once the grid cells with less than five or 10 have been removed. This finding means that the municipalities are not comparable in further analysis because the missing populations are not equal. In terms of the top municipalities in the tables, there is more change than the bottom municipalities- only Kumlinge features in all three tables. As can be seen from the three figures, Kumlinge is a very spread out municipality, having an area of 866km², but the majority is water (761km²) and has a very small population of only 308 (250m)/ 299 (1km)/297 (5km). Utilising the 250m grid, then only 39% of the population remains, and this decreases for 1km (29.4%) but increases to 85.9% for 5km. Even at the 5km scale there are municipalities that are losing a maximum of 20% of their populations when conducting further analysis on this data set.

4 Conclusion

Visually and therefore spatially, the results appear to be drastic in terms of population loss when removing the minimum population requirements for further analysis. However, when delving deeper it shows that the grid cell loss is in fact more visually exaggerated than in terms of the actual population loss which results in misinformation. For the 250m grid results, keeping only 19.2% of the polygon count looks significant, but this correlates to keeping 91.9% of the population count, and this count increases with the two larger scales (1km and 5km grids). Consequently, it is important to note that omitting almost half a million of the population is still a large amount of people, and this should be taken into consideration when utilising the three grid cell scales for further analysis and future policy making. This can be in the form of service accessibility for specific populations, such as in terms of sports services, it is important know the population's characteristics for usage prices, user demand, or simply, their location. These populations cannot be accurately represented spatially when populations are omitted.

Figure 1: 250m grid for Finland

Figure 2: 1km grid for Finland

Figure 3: 5km grid for Finland

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6 Biography

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